

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Unlocking nf-core: customising workflows for your research
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	27-28 May 2026
Time of event	12-4pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Processing and analysing 'omics datasets poses many challenges to life scientists, particularly when we need to share our methods with collaborators and scale up our research. Public and reproducible bioinformatics workflows, like those developed by nf-core, are therefore invaluable resources for the life science community.</p> <p>nf-core is a community-driven effort to provide high-quality bioinformatics workflows for common analyses including, RNAseq, mapping, variant calling, and single cell transcriptomics. A big advantage of using nf-core workflows is the ability to customise and optimise them for different computational environments, types and sizes of data, and research goals.</p> <p>This workshop will set you up with the foundational knowledge required to run and customise nf-core workflows in a reproducible manner. Over two days you will learn about the nf-core tools utility, step through the code structure of nf-core workflows, and explore the various ways to adjust workflow parameters, customise processes, and configure workflows for your computational environment, using the nf-core/maseq workflow as a hands-on example.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom.</p> <p>Dr Cali Willet and Dr Michael Geaghan led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then completed hands-on exercises giving them the chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>Facilitators provided assistance with exercises and answered questions in a shared Google Doc and in the zoom chat, in parallel to the main session.</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the Training Materials section.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p>

	Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/nf-core-2026
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 Workflow http://edamontology.org/data_1083
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This workshop is for life science researchers and bioinformaticians who are already (or soon will) be using and customising nf-core workflows. You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered.
Prerequisites	Required: Experience working in a Linux-based command-line environment and basic command line skills, including writing scripts and running tools. Recommended: Nextflow and containers
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shared live Google Doc was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • Participants were provided with access to virtual machines running on ARDC Nectar Research Cloud infrastructure. Packages, workflows and data were preinstalled.
Learning outcomes	By the end of the workshop you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the roles of Nextflow and nf-core in enabling reproducible and portable bioinformatics • Navigate the nf-core directory structure to identify key configuration files • Write and run a basic nf-core run command • Modify command-line arguments to customise the workflow • Describe Nextflow configuration hierarchy • Create and use a params file to customise workflow parameters • Create and use a custom config file to adjust resource usage • Apply external arguments not available as a workflow parameter to a process
Lead Trainers	Dr Cali Willet, Senior Bioinformatician, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney Dr Michael Geaghan, Senior Bioinformatician, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney

Facilitators	Dr Kristina Gagalova, Curtin University (Nextflow Ambassador) Dr Magdalena (Magda) Antczak, Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF)
Training materials	https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/customising-nfcore-workshop-2026/
Related work	https://zenodo.org/records/8026170